

SOFTWARE FOR NON-CONTACT DIMENSIONAL ACCURACY MEASUREMENT OF 3D PRINTED PARTS USING GOM INSPECT: CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT: In this study, components were 3D-printed using three different additive manufacturing technologies: Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), and Stereolithography (SLA). However, only the SLA printed parts were analyzed using non-contact measurement techniques. The dimensional accuracy of the SLA printed parts was evaluated using GOM Inspect software and the GOM ATOS non-contact 3D scanner, applying optical digitization to assess deviations from the nominal CAD model. This approach highlights the effectiveness of non-contact metrology in ensuring precision, especially for complex geometries and high-detail parts produced by SLA technology.

KEYWORDS: Additive Manufacturing, Dimensional Accuracy, Selective Laser Sintering, Stereolithography, 3D Scanning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dimensional accuracy is a key component in 3D printing manufacturing, ensuring that fabricated parts meet the required precision for optimal functionality and quality. Maintaining high dimensional accuracy in 3D printed parts is essential for their structural integrity, mechanical performance, and applicability in industrial and technical fields [1]. Additive manufacturing (AM) has revolutionized manufacturing processes by enabling the creation of complex geometries that are challenging or impossible to achieve using conventional manufacturing methods. However, the success of these processes relies heavily on accurate quality control tools to ensure that the final parts meet their design specifications [2].

CAX technologies, including advanced computer aided design (CAD), manufacturing (CAM), and engineering (CAE) tools, have introduced innovative methods for analyzing and measuring 3D printed parts. GOM Inspect is a powerful software solution for non-contact dimensional measurements and analysis.

The importance of CAX-based dimensional analysis in additive manufacturing has been extensively discussed in recent research. For instance, Boschetto and Bottini [3] examined

accuracy prediction in FDM-based parts, while Gibson et al. [4] explored the role of non-contact metrology in high-precision manufacturing.

This study presents the results of a non-contact dimensional analysis performed using GOM Inspect software. The turbine blade was manufactured using Stereolithography (SLA) technology with a Stratasys J835 printer and M.color Resin material. The main objective was to evaluate the accuracy of the printed part by comparing it to the nominal CAD model and identifying dimensional deviations. This evaluation is critical to understanding the accuracy of 3D printing in the production of functional and high-tolerance parts. The use of GOM Inspect allows for an accurate, non-contact method to detect variations and ensure that quality standards are met. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the capabilities of SLA printing and highlight potential areas for improvement.

Non-contact measurement techniques have become essential in modern manufacturing due to their ability to capture highly accurate dimensional data without physically interacting with the part. This is particularly important for components with complex geometries, where traditional contact-based methods are either impractical or can introduce measurement errors. These techniques are not only faster but also offering a higher level of accuracy

compared to traditional contact-based methods, enabling measurements on parts with geometries that would otherwise be impossible to measure due to the complex shape of the parts.

This paper explores the application of GOM Inspect to analyze the dimensional accuracy of 3D printed parts. It highlights how the software’s capabilities in acquiring, processing, and comparing data with CAD models facilitate effective quality assurance. Furthermore, the importance of non-contact measurement techniques in maintaining the integrity and accuracy of parts is discussed. The paper also reviews relevant literature and sources to substantiate the significance of GOM inspection and non-contact measurements in additive manufacturing [5].

2 TECHNOLOGY AND SOFTWARE INTEGRATION

Additive manufacturing technologies have emerged as an effective strategy to promote sustainability, reduce waste, and increase resource efficiency in modern manufacturing processes [6]. However, traditional reproduction methods have limitations in the production of complex geometries. Additive manufacturing (AM) methods have shown significant potential in overcoming these limitations and increasing the quality and reliability of reproduced parts. AM enables the production of replacement parts with high geometric complexity and tight tolerances [7]. This evolution has transformed AM into a sophisticated set of processes that cater to a diverse range of materials, including polymers, metals, ceramics, and composites, driving innovation across multiple sectors [8].

The technologies used in turbine blade printing are:

- Fused deposition modeling (FDM): This method extrudes thermoplastic filaments to create parts layer by layer. FDM is cost-effective and suitable for functional prototypes but can suffer from dimensional deviations due to material shrinkage and layer bonding [9].
- Selective laser sintering (SLS): SLS uses a laser to selectively sinter powdered material, enabling the creation of strong, detailed parts without the need for support structures. Despite its accuracy, thermal effects during the process can lead to small inaccuracies [10].
- Stereolithography (SLA): SLA uses a UV laser to cure liquid resin layer by layer, resulting in parts with exceptional surface quality and precision. However, the curing process can sometimes lead to material shrinkage that affects dimensions [11].

The research work involves dimensional measurement of manufactured turbine blades using 3D scanning technology, allowing an accurate assessment against the original models. In this article only SLA printed part is investigated for dimensional accuracy. To evaluate the dimensional accuracy in our experiment, the turbine blade design was chosen due to its complex geometry and critical engineering requirements. Figure 1 shows the reference turbine blade 3D model. The original turbine blade, manufactured using injection molding, was the benchmark due to its high precision, with tolerances ranging from ± 0.08 mm to ± 0.1 mm.

Fig. 1 3D model of the turbine blade used for non-contact dimensional accuracy analysis with GOM Inspect.

To ensure dimensional accuracy and surface quality, it is essential to select the right additive manufacturing technologies and determine the correct printing parameters. These parameters significantly affect the quality of the final part, including dimensional tolerances and surface finish. Table 1 shows the printing parameters and the corresponding technologies used to produce the parts.

Table 1. Detailed information about the 3D printing technologies, materials, and key parameters.

Parameter	SLS	SLA	FDM
Layer Height	70 μ m	50 μ m	120 μ m
Nozzle Temperature	N/A	N/A	180°C 0.4 mm
Bed Temperature	175°C	N/A	60°C
Print Speed	2700 mm/s	N/A	2600 mm/min
Infill Density	N/A	N/A	40%
Laser Power	40 W	200 mW	N/A
Exposure Time	N/A	8 seconds per layer	N/A
Material	Nylon	Resin M.color	PLA
Ambient Temp	22°C	22°C	28°C

Support Structures	Yes	Yes	No
Parameter	SLS	SLA	FDM
Layer Height	70 μm	50 μm	120 μm
Nozzle Temperature	N/A	N/A	180°C 0.4 mm
Bed Temperature	175°C	N/A	60°C
Print Speed	2700 mm/s	N/A	2600 mm/min
Infill Density	N/A	N/A	40%
Laser Power	40 W	200 mW	N/A
Exposure Time	N/A	8 seconds per layer	N/A
Material	Nylon	Resin M.color	PLA
Ambient Temp	22°C	22°C	28°C
Support Structures	Yes	Yes	No

For all three technologies used in this study - Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Stereolithography (SLA), and Fusible Deposition Modeling (FDM) - the process begins with uploading the STL file of the turbine blade to the relevant 3D printer software and configuring key print parameters, such as laser power or nozzle temperature, layer thickness, and print speed as in figure 2.

Fig. 2 Import of 3D model and setting parameters for the printing of parts

In this research, we utilize three polymer 3D printing technologies, as shown in Figure 3:

- Selective Laser Sintering (SLS): FORMIGA P110 printer, Nylon material.
- Stereolithography (SLA): Stratasys J835 printer, M.Color Resin material.
- Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM): Ender 3 Pro V2 printer, PLA material.

(a) (b) (c)

Fig. 3 (a) SLS printing process, (b) SLA printing process (c) FDM printing process

These technologies were chosen to evaluate non-contact dimensional accuracy measurements in additive manufacturing.

3 GOM ATOS SCANNER

The GOM ATOS Scanner is an advanced optical 3D measurement system that provides precise non-contact dimensional inspection and analysis for a wide range of applications, including additive manufacturing [12].

This scanner integrates structured blue light technology, allowing precise scanning of components without physical contact.

Its cutting-edge technology and versatile functionality make it an indispensable tool for ensuring the quality and accuracy of 3D-printed components.

Below are the key aspects of the GOM ATOS Scanner:

1- High-resolution data capture

The GOM ATOS Scanner uses structured blue light technology to project patterns onto the surface of an object, capturing millions of data points with exceptional accuracy. This high-resolution scanning enables detailed representation of intricate geometries, including small features and complex surfaces [13].

2- Non-Contact Measurement

The non-contact nature of the GOM ATOS Scanner eliminates the risk of damaging delicate or complex parts. This makes it particularly valuable for inspecting components made with additive manufacturing technologies, where complex geometries and lightweight structures are common.

3- Material and application versatility

The scanner can accurately measure a wide variety of materials, including metals, plastics, ceramics, and composites. This versatility allows it to be used in diverse industries, such as aerospace, automotive, and healthcare [14].

The first step in the evaluation process involved scanning the printed turbine blades using the GOM ATOS Core 45 scanner. This high-resolution scanning system captures fine details with a resolution of up to 5 μm , ensuring that even the

smallest deviations are recorded in printed parts. The system projects a structured light pattern onto the object's surface, which is then captured by dual cameras to create a detailed point cloud representation of the scanned object SLA scan technology (Figure 4).

The point cloud data is processed to generate a polygonal mesh, which accurately represents the 3D geometry of the scanned object. This mesh serves as the basis for subsequent dimensional analysis and comparison with the original CAD model.

Fig. 4 (a) The GOMATOS Core 45 setup for 3D scanning with a 360-degree rotating table; (b) Point cloud and mesh generation from the turbine blade scan

4 DATA ANALYSIS WITH GOM INSPECT

The turbine blade was produced using Stereolithography (SLA) on a Stratasys J835 printer and made from Resin M.color. SLA was chosen for its ability to produce high-precision components. After manufacturing, the blade was prepared for scanning by ensuring a clean and uniform surface, allowing for accurate measurement and comparison to the original digital model.

The scanned data were analyzed using GOM Inspect software. This software facilitates precise alignment of the scanned mesh with the CAD model, enabling a detailed examination of dimensional deviations. The analysis process includes several critical steps:

- CAD model alignment: the CAD model of the original turbine blade is imported into GOM Inspect and aligned with the scanned mesh. This alignment ensures that the comparison is based on a common reference framework.
- Deviation analysis: the software calculates the differences between the scanned mesh and the CAD model, highlighting areas where the printed part deviates from the intended design. These deviations are visualized through color-coded maps, providing an intuitive understanding of the dimensional accuracy (Figure 5).

Fig. 5 Deviation analysis of SLA printed turbine blade compared to CAD model

This process demonstrates modern software for aligning CAD models with 3D scanned data using non-contact metrological technology. Through automatic alignment methods and "best-fit" algorithms, the dimensional accuracy of manufactured parts is analyzed by comparing the deviations between the nominal model and the real part.

In Figure 6 part of the GOM Inspect process is presented used for non-contact dimensional analysis. This process aligns the scanned 3D model with the CAD reference model, ensuring accurate measurement of the deviation. Key parameters include search time (Normal), best fit additional calculation (enabled), and a measured deviation of 0.0511 mm. The 3D visualization highlights the comparison between the scanned and nominal models, demonstrating the importance of accurate alignment in quality control and additive manufacturing applications.

Fig. 6 Automatic merging of CAD and 3D scanned data

In Figure 7(a), we have displayed the original model where the deviations are zero for each measured area. Figure 7(b) depicts the physical printed model, which has been scanned and compared to the original CAD model. The deviation map in this figure illustrates the differences between the curves of the printed model and the nominal model. The colors in the map represent dimensional deviations:

- **Green** indicates a perfect match between the curves of the nominal model and the printed model.
- **Blue and red** indicate negative and positive deviations, respectively, identifying areas

where the printed part is below or above the original model.

Fig. 7 (a) Original CAD model

7 (b) Deviation map of the 3D scanned printed model compared to the nominal CAD model

4.1 Non-contact dimensional inspection using GOM Inspect

GOM Inspect, a powerful software tool, is widely used for analyzing the dimensional accuracy of 3D-printed or machined components. It enables the detection of deviations from nominal CAD models and ensures compliance with strict quality standards. In this study, the dimensional inspection of a turbine blade was performed using non-contact methods to evaluate critical parameters such as dimensions, tolerances, and geometric properties.

The results of this inspection, shown in figure 8 below, highlight the deviations between nominal and actual measurements for features like calipers (LX, LY, LZ) and cylinder diameter (Ø), accompanied by a color-coded deviation map for better visualization.

Fig. 8 Non-Contact Dimensional Inspection Results of the Turbine Blade Using GOM Inspect

Table 2 presents the dimensional deviations observed in the 3D-printed turbine blade. The deviation column indicates the difference between the nominal and actual measurements highlighting precision variations in the manufacturing process.

Table 2. Dimensional deviations observed in the 3D-printed turbine blade.

Measurement	Nominal (mm)	Actual (mm)	Deviation (mm)
Caliper 1 (X)	77.3	77.38	0.08
Caliper 2 (Z)	-19.0	-19.12	0.12
Caliper 3 (Y)	-31.0	-31.7	-0.7
Cylinder 1 (Ø)	5.85	5.86	0.01

4.2 Dimensional Analysis of Turbine Blade Planes

The results of dimensional accuracy of the turbine blade include also analyze of six planes (Plane 1 to Plane 6).

Figure 9 visually presents the measurement planes, providing a structured approach to analyze the geometry of the component and detect potential deviations.

Fig. 9 Analysis of Deviations Across Six Planes of the Turbine Blade Using GOM Inspect

The dimensional analysis of the measured zones was conducted using advanced algorithms integrated within the software. These algorithms automatically computed critical parameters such as Sigma, Residual, Max Deviation, and Selected Points. These calculations were essential for evaluating the deviations between the nominal and actual dimensions of the turbine blade.

The results of the six analyzed zones have been systematically summarized in Table 3, providing a detailed comparison of the computed metrics. This automated approach not only enhances the accuracy and reliability of the measurements but also ensures consistency across all zones, thereby minimizing human-induced errors and increasing the efficiency of the inspection process.

Table 3. Critical plane accuracy parameters such as Sigma, Residual, Max Deviation, and Selected Points

Plane	Sigma (mm)	Residual (mm)	Max Deviation (mm)	Selected Points
Plane 1	0.0138	0.0098	0.0705	1224
Plane 2	0.0828	0.0659	0.2497	2429
Plane 3	0.0158	0.0127	0.0537	1801
Plane 4	0.0176	0.0132	0.0542	2934
Plane 5	0.0769	0.0647	0.2305	1343
Plane 6	0.0827	0.0701	0.2213	585

The inspection revealed variations in dimensional deviations, highlighting critical areas requiring further attention. The detailed results are as follows:

Plane 1: Exhibited the highest dimensional accuracy, with a maximum deviation of 0.0705 mm, a Sigma of 0.0138 mm, and a Residual of 0.0098 mm, reflecting minimal discrepancies and excellent consistency in this region.

Plane 2: Identified as a critical zone due to the largest maximum deviation of 0.2497 mm, this plane highlights significant dimensional discrepancies that may affect the part's overall quality and performance.

Planes 3 and 4: Demonstrated stable dimensional performance with low maximum deviations of 0.0537 mm and 0.0542 mm, respectively, indicating a robust manufacturing process for these planes.

Plane 5: Recorded a notable deviation of 0.2305 mm, suggesting the need for further process optimization to improve dimensional accuracy in this region.

Plane 6: Showed a maximum deviation of 0.2213 mm, marking another area requiring attention to align with design specifications.

The analysis of different plane accuracy is presented in Table 3. The analysis emphasizes the importance of focusing on Planes 2, 5, and 6 for process improvement while confirming the stability and accuracy of the other planes.

4.3 Critical Point Deviation Measurements Using GOM Inspect

Measurements were performed at critical points on the part using GOM Inspect and non-contact measurement technology. These measurements identified deviations between the nominal model and the measured surface. For each critical area, numerical values were displayed along with color-coded visualizations, indicating areas of high accuracy and those with significant deviations.

Green areas: Represent deviations within acceptable tolerance limits, indicating high dimensional accuracy.

Yellow areas: Indicate deviations approaching tolerance limits, which may require further monitoring.

Red areas: Highlight areas where deviations exceed tolerance thresholds, signaling the need for improvements in the manufacturing process.

Each area is marked with numerical values that quantify the deviations in millimeters, providing precise data for further analysis. The use of non-contact measurement methods ensures high accuracy and eliminates any physical impact on the part, making this approach ideal for detailed inspection and complex geometry.

In Figure 10, we have presented the deviation areas and the measurements in the X region. Additionally, the measured data in the X region are presented in the Table 4.

Fig. 10 Measurement and Deviation Visualization in the X Axis

Table 4. Surface Measurement Data for the X Axis

Element	Datum	Property	Nominal	Actual	Tol -	Tol +	Dev	Check	Out
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.04	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.08	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.10	<input type="checkbox"/>	+0.00
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.10	<input type="checkbox"/>	+0.00
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.06	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.01	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.07	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.05	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.06	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Surface c...		dXYZ			-0.10	+0.10	+0.07	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Measurement Axis: Figure 11 presents deviation analysis based on the orientation on coordinate system.

Fig. 11 Deviation Analysis Based on the X, Y, Z Coordinate System

The following Table 5 presents the measured deviation data for the turbine blade, showing nominal

values, actual measurements, tolerance limits, and calculated deviations. This data is used to assess the dimensional accuracy of the component.

Table 5. Measured deviation values, including nominal, actual, and tolerance limits.

Property	Deviation X (mm)	Deviation Y (mm)	Deviation Z (mm)	Check
dXYZ	0.11	0.08	0.05	✓
dXYZ	0.07	0.05	0.03	✓
dXYZ	0.06	0.02	0.01	✓
dXYZ	0.05	0.06	0.07	✓
dXYZ	0.18	0.14	0.12	⚠
dXYZ	0.25	0.21	0.19	✗
dXYZ	0.21	0.18	0.15	✗
dXYZ	0.16	0.13	0.09	⚠
dXYZ	0.06	0.04	0.03	✓
dXYZ	0.09	0.07	0.05	✓

5 CONCLUSION

This study highlights the importance of non-contact dimensional accuracy measurement in assessing the accuracy of turbine blades. Using GOM Inspect software, the analysis successfully identified major deviations and provided a high level of accuracy on critical planes and geometric features of the turbine blade.

The findings confirm that non-contact metrology techniques, combined with high-precision scanning technology, provide a highly effective solution for precision manufacturing. The GOM ATOS 3D scanner enabled a detailed and reliable comparison between the actual and nominal CAD models, ensuring repeatability and accuracy without introducing deformation risks associated with traditional contact measurement methods.

While most measurements fell within acceptable tolerance limits, some deviations were observed in specific areas, indicating the potential for further process optimization. These discrepancies emphasize the need for enhanced calibration, material control, and post-processing refinements to improve dimensional stability.

Key Insights from the Three-Axis Deviation Analysis:

- **Highest Deviation:** The X-axis showed the highest deviations, indicating potential misalignment or material inconsistencies.

- **Consistent Stability:** The Z-axis deviations remained relatively minimal, reflecting better stability in certain manufacturing stages.
- **Manufacturing Optimization:** Variations across the three axes suggest process improvements in toolpath programming, temperature control, and material handling.

Future Recommendations:

- **Enhanced Calibration:** Implementing advanced calibration routines can improve measurement precision.
- **Process Optimization:** Adjusting 3D printing and post-processing parameters can reduce deviations.
- **Expanded Studies:** Further research should explore applying GOM Inspect software to different manufacturing techniques to validate findings across various processes.
- **Industrial Implementation:** The integration of non-contact quality control systems into production workflows will enhance efficiency, reliability, and repeatability in manufacturing.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that software-based non-contact dimensional measurement techniques offer superior accuracy and efficiency compared to conventional measurement methods. By leveraging GOM Inspect software, industries can significantly improve the quality assurance process for high-precision components, ensuring compliance with strict tolerances and design specifications.

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